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History of Physical Culture and Sports

PHYSICAL CULTURE IN PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF STUDENTS

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Abstract

To correctly assess the impact of physical culture on the professional activities of University graduates, it is necessary first of all to take into account the importance and role of physical culture in the life of a person as a whole, regardless of their professional affiliation, nature and type of activity. It is necessary to determine the basics of a healthy lifestyle, physical improvement, and then take into account the characteristics of those who specialize in a particular type of professional activity, taking into account working conditions. Each category of workers has different health requirements. The article analyzes these factors in the development of physical culture.

Keywords: physical culture, sport, society, person, training.

I. INTRODUCTION

At its core, physical culture has an appropriate motor activity in the form of physical exercises that allow you to effectively form the necessary skills and abilities, physical abilities, optimize health and performance.

The result of activity in physical culture is physical fitness and the degree of perfection of motor skills, a high level of development of vital forces, sports achievements, moral, aesthetic, and intellectual development.

So, physical culture should be considered as a special kind of cultural activity, the results of which are useful for society and the individual. In the social life in the education system, education in the sphere of organization of labour, everyday life, healthy recreation, physical culture develops its educational, recreational, economic and cultural value that contributes to such social currents, as physical motion, i.e. the joint activity of people on the use, dissemination and multiplication of the physical values

The professional orientation of physical culture is the basis that unites all its other components.

Objective and subjective indicators are the criteria that can be used to judge the formation of a person's physical culture. Based on them, it is possible to identify the essential properties and measure of physical culture in the activity.

In accordance with the criteria, a number of levels of physical culture of the individual can be distinguished.

The pre-nominal level develops spontaneously. The reasons for it lie in the sphere of consciousness in relation to students and are related to dissatisfaction with the program offered by teachers, the content of classes and extracurricular activities, its semantic and General cultural potential; complicated interpersonal relations with the teacher. Students have no need for cognitive activity, and knowledge is shown at the level of familiarity with the educational material. The connection of physical culture with the formation of the future specialist's personality and the process of his professional training is denied. The motivational sphere is dominated by a negative or indifferent attitude. In the classroom, such students are passive, and they reject the field of extracurricular activities. The level of their physical capabilities may vary.

The potential level is based on a positive conscious attitude of students to physical culture for self — improvement and professional activity. They have the necessary knowledge, beliefs, practical skills that allow them to competently perform a variety of physical culture and sports activities under the supervision and advice of teachers and experienced friends. Cognitive activity is manifested both in the field of sports shows and in the development of popular science literature.

The creative level is typical for students who are convinced of the value value and the need to use physical culture for the development and realization of personal opportunities. These students are characterized by thorough knowledge of physical culture, they possess the skills and abilities of physical self-improvement, organization of a healthy lifestyle, use of physical culture for rehabilitation under high nervous and emotional loads and after diseases; they creatively introduce physical culture in professional activities, in family life. After graduation, they show initiative in many areas of life.

II. METHODOLOGY

The methodological basis of the research consists of: ideas about the methodology of scientific knowledge (B.A. Ashmarina, M.R. Kudaeva, F.A. Kuzina, B.A. Raizberga, K.D. Chermita); systemic (I.V. Blauberg, E.G. Yudin and others) and activity-based (V.V. Davydov, A.N. Leontiev) approaches to the educational process; ideas about a personality-oriented approach to the process of teaching physical culture (E.V. Bondarevskaya); modern scientific ideas about the relationship between the intellectual and bodily-motor components of a student's physical education (M.Ya. Vilensky, V.N. Kurys, V.P. Lukyanenko, K.D. Chermit, etc.); modern approaches to higher education in the field of physical culture (V.K. Balsevich, M.Ya. Vilensky, A.A. Gorelov, S.P. Evseev, L.I. Lubysheva, and others); modern concepts and health-saving technologies of physical culture of student youth.

III. DISCUSSION

One of the main vectors of modernizing modern education is the implementation of the idea of its continuity (Darinsky A. B., Zinchenko G. P., Rimareva I. I., Kuleshov I. V.). The condition of continuity of physical training of the student of educational institutions of sphere of physical culture, the theory of continuous education give us reason to believe that the establishment and the implementation of the mentioned ideas, of course, has enduring value for the contemporary society and, in particular, for the sphere of physical culture, provided that the substantive provisions of the continuity of education are becoming more effective in the specific field of human activity.

The process of increasing the flow of information in the field of education, the necessity of the processing in a short time, the use of innovative technical training define clearly expressed tendency of intensification of educational process in universities (Radeva G. V. Perunov, V. I., Boychenko S. F., Baronenko V. A., Rapoport L. A., Chermit K. D.). Progressive tensions mental activity, and with it the increasing lack of exercise cause a decline in performance of functional systems of organism of student and his physical health in General, as you move from Junior to senior courses. According to researchers, the dynamics of the state of physical fitness of students, as a component of personal culture, is not positive during their studies at the University, and the level of their physical fitness is quite low (Ozolin N. G., Izaak S. I., Kabachkov V. A., Tyapin A. N., etc.). This situation is also complicated by the fact that in the rating of students' values, the state of their own health occupies a very modest place (V. P. Kushmanova, F. L. Dolenko).

The above mentioned applies to students of higher education institutions in the field of physical culture in a multiple measure due to the specifics of their educational activities, which are significantly different from those for students of other universities. The difference is almost in the parity ratio of pronounced mental and bodily-motor activities.

IV. RESULTS

Physical education of students as a pedagogical system of physical improvement of a person remains a key concept for General comprehensive education and, especially, in the formation of physical culture of the individual. In higher education institutions, the contribution of education in the field of physical culture should consist in providing students with all aspects of knowledge about human life, about their health and healthy lifestyle, as well as in mastering practical skills that ensure the development and improvement of the individual. Negative trends that characterize the level of physical development and health of students, skeptical attitude of students to the principles of a healthy lifestyle, ignoring the means and opportunities of physical culture and sports for full-fledged and active leisure, " education of will, character, purposefulness require new approaches to the organization of physical culture and sports activities. Qualitative rethinking and creative reform of the process of physical education by strengthening the humanitarian direction of physical culture significantly increases its culture-forming essence and provides the basis for a constructive solution to this problem.

Socio-economic and political transformations of modern Russia create conditions for the formation of physical culture and sports activity of young people by giving each student the freedom to choose the types, means and forms of organizing their own physical activity, taking into account individual characteristics, morphofunctional features and socio-psychological factors, their values, interests and needs. A powerful incentive for physical culture and sports activity of students is the health potential of physical culture and sports.

The problem of assessing the state of individual health and monitoring changes in its level is becoming increasingly important, especially for people who are exposed to high psychoemotional and physical stress.

A radical conceptual transition in health policy is required from considering citizens as passive consumers of medical services to understanding the need to strengthen the physical and spiritual health of a person through joint efforts of the state, public organizations and individuals. The formation of individual, personal-oriented health improvement programs aimed at strengthening the health of a particular person, improving their adaptation to academic and work activities has not yet found its place in educational systems, including in higher education institutions. In order to preserve and develop the spiritual, intellectual and physical potential of humanity throughout its development, it forms appropriate social institutions. It is difficult to overestimate the role of religion, art, and literature in preserving human spirituality. Intellectual potential is preserved and developed by the education and upbringing system and science. For physical potential are responsible for physical education and sport, health, system, recreational activities, etc. Education should play a significant role in shaping the culture of the individual, in increasing the intellectual, physical and spiritual potential of a person. The future of Russia will largely be determined by what graduates of schools and universities will be like.

V. CONCLUSION

It is obvious that the contribution of physical education to General higher education should consist in providing students with all aspects of knowledge about human life, about their health and healthy lifestyle, as well as in mastering the entire Arsenal of practical skills that ensure the preservation and promotion of health, development and improvement of their psychophysical abilities and personal qualities. Only such a humanitarian direction of physical culture in higher education can serve as the basis for a significant increase in its cultural functions. With the help of knowledge obtained in the discipline "Physical culture", students should create a holistic view of the processes and phenomena occurring in nature, more fully understand the possibilities of modern scientific methods of knowledge of nature and master them at the level of professional functions. The knowledge obtained during the development of the mandatory minimum content of the program material on physical culture should form the basis of ideas about a healthy lifestyle and provide a theoretical basis for the formation of skills and abilities for physical self-improvement of the individual throughout life. This approach to physical education of students entails the rejection of traditional models of the University pedagogical process and the need to review the goals of the physical education process in the direction of developing its humanizing and cultural functions at the present stage.

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ФИЗИЧЕСКАЯ КУЛЬТУРА В ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПОДГОТОВКЕ СТУДЕНТОВ

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Аннотация

Чтобы правильно оценить влияние физической культуры на профессиональную деятельность выпускников вуза, необходимо прежде всего учитывать значение и роль физической культуры в жизни человека в целом, независимо от его профессиональной принадлежности, характера и вида деятельности. Необходимо определить основы здорового образа жизни, физического совершенствования, а затем учесть особенности тех, кто специализируется на том или ином виде профессиональной деятельности, с учетом условий труда. Каждая категория работников имеет свои требования к здоровью. В статье анализируются эти факторы в развитии физической культуры.

Ключевые слова: физическая культура, спорт, общество, личность, обучение.

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